

1971

c. November

I went from Bushehr to Tepe Yahya where I took part in the excavations. There I recieved a telegram from David Stronach saying " Your presence is required in Teheran immediatly. Fearing a serious situation I rushed to Teheran to find out that all that was expected of me was to give a curriculum vitae to the Head of Excavations of the Iranian Archaeological Service. He seemed rather surprised that I had come in person. He seemed embarrassed because the Iranian Archaeological Service was supposed to have curriculum vitae of all archaeologists active in Iran, but did not. I was not called to see the Director General or any member of the Security Services. Nor although the Iranian Archaeological Service could have withdrawn my permit if there was any doubt at all about my actions did they do so. However they did tell me not to survey on the coast North of Bandar Abbas this year though they did not alter my permit letter at all. It was emphasized to me that this restriction was imposed by the Archaeological Service for my own safty. They had no objections to my work on the coast at Minab. Thereupon I returned to Tepe Yahya.

David Stronach suggested that he ask the Archaeological Service in Mid August whether I could survey on a larger area of the coast for which I still had wtitten permission. I was glad to accept this offer.

David undertook to communicate the results of his conversation to me at two addresses. A letter was sent to the Yahya Expedition which arrived after the end of the excavation. No communication was ever sent to the other address, nor when I made a 2,000 mile round trip to Teheran had any information been left there. Nor was anything subsequently sent to my address in Bandar Abbas. So I did not hear about David's conversation until the end of October. He told me then that the Archaeological Service had told him that they did not wish me to survey this year on any part of the Persian Gulf coast. The Museum authorities never informed me personally of this. They were most helpful, and said that they would have no objection to my continuing survey in the next year.

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